

Influence of Light on Some Colloids.

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In publications (*Kolloid Z.*, 1922, **31**, 16 ; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, **33**) from these laboratories the influence of light on some properties of colloids has been investigated. We have observed that sols can be divided into two classes. In one class the stability of the sol towards electrolytes increases and in the other the stability decreases on exposure to light. With some sols the electric conductivity increases whilst with others it decreases on exposure to light. Measurements of the absorption spectra of the exposed and unexposed sols showed more marked absorption of light in the cases of ferric hydroxide, arsenious sulphide and Prussian blue and less absorption in the cases of gum dammar, mastic, etc. We have also shown that sols of manganese dioxide, ceric hydroxide, copper ferrocyanide and Odèn sulphur coagulate completely on exposure to sunlight.

In this communication we have investigated the influence of sunlight and light from a thousand watt gas-filled tungsten filament lamp on the (a) coagulation, (b) electric conductivity, and (c) extinction coefficient of sols of stannic hydroxide, aluminium hydroxide, thorium hydroxide, antimony sulphide, mercuric sulphide, arsenious sulphide, cupric ferrocyanide and uranium ferrocyanide.

The sols were exposed to light in small stoppered Jena glass bottles or silica vessels. The extinction coefficients were determined by a Nutting's spectrophotometer.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Stannic hydroxide.

The stannic hydroxide was prepared at the ordinary temperature by adding ammonium hydroxide to stannic chloride. The stannic hydroxide thus obtained was washed two or three times to free it from electrolytes partially. On further addition of water it turned immediately to a sol, which was dialysed for 10 days.

TABLE I.

Concentration = 6.66 gms. of SnO_2 per litre. Volume of mixture = 10 c.c. Amount of sol taken = 1 c.c. Time allowed for coagulation = 1 hour.

Electrolyte used.	Amount needed for coagulation.		
	Unexposed.	Exposed.	
N/2.5-KCl	0.80 c.c.	0.55	The sol was exposed for 169 hrs. 15 mins. to sunlight.
N/500-BaCl ₂	2.50	2.00	

Electric conductivity at 25°.

Sp. conductivity for unexposed sol	...	...	0.005794 mhos.
Sp. conductivity for sol exposed to sunlight for 237 hrs.			0.006164 ..

Extinction coefficients.

Sol.	Extinction coefficient.		
Unexposed Sb_2S_3	...	...	0.0
Sb_2S_3 exposed to sunlight for 201 hrs. and 40 mins.			0.1

Aluminium hydroxide.

Aluminium hydroxide was precipitated by ammonium hydroxide on aluminium nitrate solution at the ordinary temperature. The precipitate was completely freed from electrolytes by repeated washings and was peptised to a turbid sol by the addition of a few drops of dilute hydrochloric acid.

TABLE II.

Concentration = 15.42 gms. of Al_2O_3 per litre. Total volume taken = 10 c.c. Amount of sol taken = 0.5 c.c. Time allowed for coagulation = 1 hour.

Electrolyte used.	Amount of electrolyte required for coagulation.		
	Unexposed sol.	Sol exposed for 25 hrs. to sunlight.	
N-KCl	3.25 c.c.	3.0 c.c.	
N/500-K ₂ SO ₄	4.10	4.0	

Electric conductivity at 25°.

Sp. conductivity for sol kept in the dark.	...	...	0.001821 mhos.
Sp. conductivity for sol. exposed to sunlight for 25 mins.	...	...	0.001888

Extinction coefficient.

Sol.	Extinction coefficient.	
Unexposed $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$	...	... 0.8
$\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ exposed for 94 hrs.	..	... 0.72

Thorium hydroxide.

A solution of Kahlbaum's pure thorium nitrate was filtered and boiled for about an hour, and the boiled solution was subjected to hot dialysis for 7 days. A clear transparent sol of thorium hydroxide was obtained.

TABLE III.

Concentration = 6.1 gms. of ThO_2 per litre. Volume of mixture = 10 c.c. Amount of sol taken = 0.5 c.c. Time allowed for coagulation = 1 hour.

Electrolyte used.	Amount needed for coagulation.	
	Unexposed sol.	Sol exposed for 58 hrs. 45 mins. to sunlight.
5.33 N-KCl	1.85 c.c.	1.25 c.c.
N/50- K_2SO_4	0.60	0.50
N/100- K_3 -citrate	1.30	0.60

Electric conductivity at 25°.

Sp. conductivity for sol kept in the dark.	Sp. conductivity for sol exposed for 106 hrs, 10 mins. to sunlight.
0.009581 mhos.	0.01284 mhos.
0.009796	0.01278

Extinction coefficients.

Sol.	Extinction coefficient.	
$\text{Tb}(\text{OH})_3$ sol kept in the dark	...	... 0.03
Sol exposed to sunlight for 75 hrs. 30 mins.	...	... 0.07

Mercuric sulphide.

Mercuric oxide was precipitated by the action of pure potassium hydroxide solution on mercuric chloride solution. The precipitate was freed from alkali and chloride by repeated washing first with cold and then with hot water. The purified mercuric oxide was boiled in a Jena flask with conductivity water. To the saturated solution of mercuric oxide thus obtained a slow current of hydrogen sulphide

was passed and a black sol of mercuric sulphide was obtained. The excess of hydrogen sulphide was removed by passing a current of hydrogen. By this method one can readily obtain a pure sol of mercuric sulphide.

TABLE IV.

Concentration of sol = 0.11 gm. of HgS per litre. Volume of mixture = 5 c.c. Amount of sol taken = 2.5 c.c. Time allowed for coagulation = 1 hour.

Electrolyte used.	Amount needed for coagulation.	
	Unexposed sol.	Sol exposed to sunlight for 88 hrs. 15 mins.
N/10-KCl	1.2 c.c.	0.4 c.c.
N/40-BaCl ₂	0.3	0.15

Electric conductivity at 25°.

Sp. conductivity for sol kept in the dark	...	...	0.0002146 mhos.
Sp. conductivity for sol exposed to sunlight for 147 hrs. 45 mins.			0.0002869.

Extinction coefficients.

Sol.	Extinction coefficient.	
HgS kept in the dark	...	1.25
Sol exposed to sunlight for 117 hrs. 5 mins.		1.40

Antimony sulphide.

Hydrogen sulphide was passed through a solution of potassium antimony tartrate. An orange coloured sol of antimony sulphide was obtained which was freed from sulphuretted hydrogen and tartrate by dialysis at the ordinary temperature for 10 days.

TABLE V.

Concentration of sol = 0.53 gm. of Sb₂S₃ per litre. Vol. of mixture = 10 c. c. Amount of sol taken = 1 c.c. Time allowed for coagulation = 1 hour.

Electrolyte used.	Amount needed for coagulation.	
	Unexposed sol.	Sol exposed to sunlight for 27 hrs 30 mins.
N-KCl	0.55 c. c.	0.80 c. c.
N/40-BaCl ₂	0.80	1.60

Electric conductivity at 25.°

The sol coagulated after 52 hrs. and 50 minutes' exposure in a glass vessel so that the electric conductivity and extinction coefficients could not be noted.

In the following experiments antimony and arsenious sulphide sols were exposed to light in silica vessels.

Antimony sulphide.

The sol was prepared in the usual way but was not subjected to dialysis as it was a clear one.

TABLE VI.

Concentration of the sol = 0.9430 gm. of Sb_2S_3 per litre. Vol. of mixture = 5 c. c. Amount of sol taken = 1 c. c. Time allowed for coagulation = 1 hour.

Electrolyte used.	Amount needed for coagulation.	Nature of sol taken.
N/10-KCl	2.2 c. c.	Kept in the dark.
	2.2	Exposed to light from a 1000-Watt lamp for 3 hrs.
	2.5	" " " " " 4½ "
	2.5	" " " to sunlight for 3 hrs.
	2.4	Exposed to light from a 1000-Watt lamp for 9 "
	2.4	Kept in the dark.
	2.5	" " "
	2.2	Exposed to sunlight for 13 hrs. 18 mins.

Electric conductivity at 25.°

Sp. conductivity for sol kept in the dark.	Sp. conductivity for sol exposed to light.	Nature of light and time.
0.000627	0.000629	1000-Watt lamp for 3 hrs.
	0.000632	" " " 4½ hrs.
	0.000653	" " " 9 "
	0.000682	Sunlight for 3 hrs.
	0.00149	" 13 hrs. 18 mins.

Extinction coefficients.

Sol.	Extinction coefficient.
Sb_2S_3 kept in the dark	0.60
Sb_2S_3 exposed to light from a 1,000 Watt lamp for 4½ hrs.	0.49
Sb_2S_3 exposed to light from a 1,000 Watt lamp for 9 hours	0.52

Arsenious sulphide.

The sol was prepared by passing hydrogen sulphide in a concentrated solution of arsenious oxide in water. In order to free it from hydrogen sulphide a current of hydrogen was passed.

TABLE VII.

Concentration of the sol = 52.79 gms As_2S_3 per litre. Vol. of mixture = 5 c. c. Amount of sol taken = 1 c. c. Time allowed for coagulation = 1 hour.

Electrolyte used.	Amount needed for coagulation.	Nature of sol.
N/10-KCl	3.10 c. c.	Kept in the dark-
	3.20	Exposed to sunlight for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr.
	3.10	„ „ 1 „
	3.05	„ „ 2 hrs.
	3.00	„ „ 3 „
	2.90	„ 4 hrs. 45 mins.

Electric conductivity.

Sp. conductivity for sol kept in the dark.	Sp. conductivity for sol exposed to sunlight.	Time of exposure.
0.000303	0.000364	1 hr.
	0.000439	2 hrs.
	0.000502	3 „

Extinction coefficients.

Sol.	Extinction coefficients.
As_2S_3 kept in the dark	... 1.73
As_2S_3 exposed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour to sunlight	... 1.48
As_2S_3 exposed for 3 hours to sun light	... 1.83

Uranium ferrocyanide.

Solutions of uranium nitrate and potassium ferrocyanide were mixed at the ordinary temperature and a brownish red sol of uranium ferrocyanide was obtained in presence of an excess of potassium ferrocyanide. The sol was dialysed for 12 days in order to free it from potassium ferrocyanide.

TABLE VIII.

Concentration of sol = 4.0 gms. uranium ferrocyanide per litre.
 Vol. of the mixture = 5. c. c. Amount of sol taken = 1 c. c. Time
 allowed for coagulation = 1 hour.

Electrolyte used.	Amount needed for coagulation.	
	Unexposed sol.	Exposed for 10 hrs. 20 mins.
N/25-KCl	2.5 c. c.	2.3 c. c.
N/40-BaCl ₂	1.9	1.7

Electric conductivity at 25.°

Completely coagulated after 33 hrs. 15 mins'. exposure to sun-
 ight. Hence electric conductivity could not be determined.

Extinction coefficients.

Sol.	Extinction coefficient.
Uranium ferrocyanide kept in in dark	3.8
Uranium ferrocyanide exposed to sunlight for 23 hrs. 5 mins	2.2

In the following experiments uranium and cupric ferrocyanide
 sols were exposed to sunlight in silica vessels.

Uranium ferrocyanide.

TABLE IX.

Concentration of the sol = 0.955 gm. uranium ferrocyanide per
 litre. Vol. of mixture = 5 c. c. Amount of sol taken = 1 c. c. Time
 allowed for coagulation = 1 hour.

Electrolyte used.	Amount needed for coagulation.	Nature of sol.
N/10-KCl	1.6 c. c.	Kept in the dark.
	1.55	Exposed to sunlight for 2½ hours.
	1.50	" " " " 5 "
	1.40	Kept in the dark.
	1.60	Exposed to sunlight for 1 hour.

The sol coagulated so that the conductivity and extinction co-
 efficient results could not be noted.

Cupric ferrocyanide.

Concentrated solutions of cupric sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide (excess) were mixed together. The mixture was allowed to dialyse for 20 days.

TABLE X.

Concentration of the sol = 22.58 gms. of cupric ferrocyanide per litre.
Vol. of the mixture = 5 c.c. Amount of sol taken = 1 c.c. Time allowed for coagulation = 1 hour.

Electrolyte used.	Amount needed for coagulation.	Nature of sol.
N/10-KCl	0.65 c. c.	Kept in the dark.
	0.70	Exposed to sunlight for 1 hour.
	0.85	Exposed to sunlight for 2 hours.
	0.75	Exposed to sunlight for 3 ,,
	0.85	Kept in the dark.
	0.80	Exposed to sunlight for 25 hours.

Electric conductivity.

Sp. conductivity for sol kept in dark.	Sp. conductivity for sol exposed to sunlight.	Time of exposure.
0.000184	0.000134	1 hour.
	0.000165	2 hrs.
	0.000168	3 ,,

Extinction coefficients.

Sol.	Extinction coefficient.	
Sol kept in the dark	...	2.98
Sol exposed to sunlight for 2 hrs....	.	2.48
,, ,, ,, 3 ,,	...	8.08

The experimental results on the influence of light on colloids show that sols of $\text{Sn}(\text{OH})_4$, $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_4$, $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ and HgS become unstable towards electrolytes on exposure to light. The electric conductivity of these sols increases on exposure.

On the other hand, sols of Sb_2S_3 , As_2S_3 , uranium ferrocyanide and cupric ferrocyanide, when exposed to light for a short time,

become stable, but on longer exposure they become unstable towards electrolytes. On further exposure Sb_2S_3 , HgS , and uranium ferrocyanide coagulate completely.

In papers (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, **162**, 237 ; **168**, 209; *Kolloid Z.* 1927, **42**, 120) published from these laboratories we have shown that sols of ferric hydroxide, aluminium hydroxide, stannic hydroxide, etc., become more conducting, less viscous and less stable towards electrolytes on ageing. Our results show that the effect of light is of the same type as that of ageing on the hydroxide sols. We (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, **29**, 659 ; *Kolloid Z.*, 1926, **38**, 14 ; **39**, 346) have also shown that sols of arsenious sulphide, antimony sulphide and cupric and uranium ferrocyanides are appreciably hydrolysed in aqueous solutions and this hydrolysis makes the sol more stable towards electrolytes. Moreover we have also shown that on ageing the sols become more hydrolysed and more stable towards electrolytes up to a limiting value. The foregoing results show that under the influence of light these sols become more hydrolysed and more stable towards electrolytes when exposed for a short time especially in silica vessels. On longer exposure the sols become unstable towards electrolytes. This behaviour is due to the fact that in the cases of arsenious and antimony sulphides, the stabilising electrolyte hydrogen sulphide is oxidised by air. Moreover, several of the sulphides are oxidised also to sulphur and thionic compounds. In the case of the ferrocyanides the stabilising ferrocyanide ions decompose on longer exposure making the sols unstable towards electrolytes. The first effect of light is to increase the degree of hydrolysis of the sulphide, the ferrocyanides and other easily hydrolysable sols and hence increases their stability towards electrolytes. This effect is more than counterbalanced by the oxidation or the decomposition of the stabilising ion on longer exposure rendering the sols unstable towards electrolytes and their subsequent coagulation on long exposure.

Our experimental results show that in general the effect of light on sols is in the same direction as that of ageing. The light effect seems more pronounced than the time effect.

The measurements of extinction coefficients of sols as recorded in this paper do not warrant any definite conclusion regarding the absorptive power of exposed and unexposed sols. Further work in this line is in progress in this laboratory.

Summary.

1. Sols of stannic hydroxide, aluminium hydroxide, thorium hydroxide and mercuric sulphide become unstable towards mono- and bi-valent ions on exposure to light.

2. Arsenious sulphide, antimony sulphide, uranium ferrocyanide and cupric ferrocyanide when exposed to light for a short time become stable in their coagulation by electrolytes; but on longer exposure they become unstable.

3. On prolonged exposure sols of antimony sulphide, mercuric sulphide and uranium ferrocyanide coagulate completely.

4. Exposed sols of stannic hydroxide, aluminium hydroxide, thorium hydroxide, mercuric sulphide, antimony sulphide and arsenious sulphide are more electrically conducting than the respective unexposed sols.

5. Measurements of extinction coefficients of sols show that in some cases the exposed sols show more absorption of light than the unexposed ones. No general conclusion can be arrived at regarding light absorption of sols on exposure to light.